

MEASURING THE THERMAL EXPANSION OF POLYMERS AND COMPOSITES BY SPECKLE PATTERN INTERFEROMETRY

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ABSTRACT

The application of electronic speckle pattern interferometry (ESPI) to the thermal expansion (CTE) characterization of polymers and composites is demonstrated. ESPI is an optical technique requiring no contact to the sample or calibration with a reference material. The sample expands freely, and simultaneous measurements along two perpendicular axes give the full in-plane CTE tensor. Relatively large samples can be measured with minimal preparation, and the CTE has been measured through the glass transition of materials. The precision and reproducibility of the method correspond to those of conventional dilatometers. Some precautions and requirements proper to the ESPI technique are discussed. Measured CTEs range from 5 to over 100×10^{-6} .

INTRODUCTION

The heterogeneous and usually anisotropic structure of composite materials makes their experimental thermoelastic characterization difficult. Particular attention must be paid to sample geometry, test configuration, and testing conditions, as is reflected in the separate formulation of testing norms such as by ASTM for composites. The deformation fields depend on the distribution and orientation of the reinforcement fibers and thus can be biased by inappropriate sample geometries. Furthermore, for polymer composites, the properties vary significantly through the glass transition or softening temperature of the matrix, making the test setup at low temperatures inappropriate for a higher temperature range. Several major inconveniences are encountered with the thermal expansion (CTE) measurements on composite materials using conventional dilatometers. The sample preparation is involved and thus costly. The required samples are typically small, and their faces normal to the axis on which the expansion is measured must be flat and parallel in order to ensure the contact between the extensometer probe and the sample over the entire temperature range. For multiphase materials, this can pose problems with samples that deform inhomogeneously over the probe contact surface. A further difficulty lies in ensuring that the sample's axes correspond to the axes of the material along which the CTE values are desired. The CTE is low in the predominant fiber direction and sensitive to small angle changes. The small sample size makes it difficult to control the fiber angle with respect to the sample's main axes. Composite laminates for which the CTE is desired are often thin, which makes it difficult to provide sample with small aspect ratios as are often needed in dilatometers. Finally, the probe exerts a pressure on the sample that can lead to a slight indentation of the area under the probe tip and thus give decreasing linear expansion when measuring soft or viscoelastic samples.

Several interferometric methods have been successfully applied to the thermomechanical characterization of composite materials [1, 2]. Fizeau [3] interferometry is particularly adapted for measuring very small expansions, such as those of carbon fiber-reinforced composites parallel to the fibers. It is however less appropriate for the range of deformations and sample sizes examined here. Holographic [2] and laser moiré interferometry [4-7] are relatively widely used for deformations under mechanical as well as thermal loads. The latter gives a good resolution and

covers a large range of deformations, but requires the application of a diffraction grating. This procedure is delicate, and the expansion of the epoxy substrate of the grating may lead to measurement errors for anisothermal tests. Electronic speckle pattern interferometry (ESPI) appears to hold the best promise for quantitative thermal expansion measurements on composites. It is a full field measurement method with which deformations under mechanical and thermal loads can be measured along three perpendicular axes without contact to the sample [8-13]. The CTE can be measured on samples with relatively large dimensions and aspect ratios, such as plates or entire components [10]. Sample preparation is easy and requires a minimum of manipulation. In this paper, we present the application of ESPI to the measurement of deformations for the quantitative characterization of thermal expansion properties of polymeric composite materials.

DESCRIPTION OF ESPI: PRINCIPLE OF THE MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUE

The speckle effect is produced by the interference between the reflected rays when a non-specular, dispersing surface is illuminated with a laser beam. The pattern is defined by the microscopically rough topography of the sample surface. Any deformation of the surface results in a change of the speckle pattern. A correlation of the speckle patterns for an object in a reference state and in a deformed state gives information on the deformation of the object's surface. This is typically done by gray-level subtraction of two video interferograms and some additional digital image analysis. For each interferogram, three or four images of the interference pattern are taken with a phase shift of the laser beam of 120° or 90°, respectively, and they are combined to give a phase image, which holds information not only on the amount, but also on the direction of deformation.

Two measuring configurations, illustrated in Fig.1, give components of in- and out-of-plane deformation. The in-plane displacements are given by the relative phase shift of two imaging beams. The out-of-plane displacements, i.e. parallel to the optical axis (line parallel to the viewing direction) are obtained from the amount of phase shift of an imaging beam with respect to a reference beam. One can thus measure the 3-D deformation of an object under a load. The sensitivity of the measurements are given by the wavelength of the laser and, for in-plane measurements, by the angle between the imaging beams and the optical axis as shown in Fig.1:

$$\text{out-of-plane: } s = \frac{\lambda}{2} \quad \text{in-plane: } s = \frac{\lambda}{2 \sin \theta} \quad (1)$$

SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

The Newport HC speckle pattern interferometry system used for this study consists of speckle and moiré interferometers, a hardware control and data acquisition system, and an image analysis facility (Fig.2). The software Optocat® was used for the image processing. The interferometer operates with near infrared laser diodes with a wavelength of 830nm. This gives an out-of-plane measurement sensitivity of 0.415µm/fringe. The distance between the front mirrors forming the

Figure 1. Measurement of deformations by ESPI

Figure 2. Schematic of the system for the materials characterization by ESPI

imaging beam sources was 295mm and the distance to the object was 700mm in the present setup. The measuring sensitivity is thus $2.0\mu\text{m}/\text{fringe}$ for both in-plane axes. Since information on the displacement gradient is conveyed by the phase of the fringes, the effective sensitivity is about an order of magnitude higher, or about 50nm. This is limited by the noise, which is fairly high with speckle pattern interferometry due to the random nature of the speckle pattern.

In the present study, images were recorded with a 512×512 pixel Sony CCD camera operating at 25Hz. A 105mm / f2.8 D Nikkor macro lens was used on the front end of the viewing system. The distance of 700mm between the speckle unit gave an imaging field of about $24\text{mm} \times 36\text{mm}$. The resulting calibration of the video monitor screen was 0.067 and 0.046mm/pixel in the x and y directions, respectively. The spatial resolution achieved is of the order of twenty pixels or a millimeter. Different combinations of divergent mirrors for the imaging beams and lenses for the viewing extend the range of sample sizes from about 5×5 to $200 \times 150\text{mm}^2$. The time required for a measurement is determined by the frequency of the video camera and the speed of the shutters and phase shifting devices. It is approximately half a second for each axis for the system used here.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Thermal expansion tests were performed on varied samples ranging from $\phi 6\text{mm}$ rods of unidirectional pultruded composites to plates measuring about $30 \times 20\text{mm}^2$, with thicknesses between 0.15 and 2mm. The composite samples were compression molded and cut to shape, while the others were cut from as-received stock. Sample preparation consisted simply of an application of a fine chalk spray to the sample surface. The materials tested were: glass, stainless steel, copper, and aluminum; neat polycarbonate (PC), polymethyl-methacrylate (PMMA), polyamide (PA-6), polypropylene (PP), polyetherimide (PEI), and a dendrimer-modified epoxy; unidirectional (UD) and 2-D random glass fiber-reinforced PP, UD glass fiber-reinforced PEI, aramid and carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy, and carbon fiber-reinforced polyetheretherketone (PEEK). The first five materials, whose CTE is well documented, were used to calibrate the ESPI thermal expansion tests. The composition of the composites is given in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Description of the composite materials tested

Material	matrix	fiber	fiber orient.	ϕ (vol%)
GE GMT	PP	glass	2-D random	15-18
ICI Plytron	PP	glass	UD	38
PEI/glass	PEI	glass	UD	52
APC2	PEEK	AS4 carbon	UD	62

A schematic of the setup is given in Fig.3. The thermal expansion tests were conducted in a cylindrical oven insulated with 75mm thick ceramic foam walls. The interferometer optics were located outside the oven enclosure, and measurements were made through a double-pane window consisting of two highly polished 5mm pyrex disks with an air gap of 5mm. The samples were placed on a support consisting of three $\phi 1.5\text{mm}$ steel bearings adhesively bonded to a fused quartz platform. This platform was placed on a quartz column which was firmly connected to the

Figure 3. Experimental setup for the thermal expansion characterization by ESPI

vibration damping table. This setup allows circulation of air around the sample and thus a fast stabilization of the sample's temperature. Thinner, more compliant samples were placed directly on a platform coated with graphite in order to reduce friction between the samples and the support to a minimum. Order of magnitude calculations based on the mass of the samples and estimated friction coefficients between the bearing surface and the various sample materials shows that errors due to friction at the contact between sample and platform, such as hysteresis for heating/cooling, can be neglected. The temperature was controlled by an all-purpose process controller, and measured directly at the sample surface by a K-type thermocouple. Temperature values were recorded to $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$.

The thermal load was applied in temperature steps of $2\text{-}10^\circ\text{C}$, and measurements were made after a stabilization time depending on the temperature interval and the sample size, mass, and thermal characteristics. It was found that an appropriate temperature step size and a sufficient stabilization time were important for obtaining reliable results. Tests were conducted on the UD PP/glass composite, which has a relatively low thermal conductivity, to determine the limiting values of these experimental parameters. Fig.4 shows a plot of the temperature as measured at the sample surface and of the sample elongation as a function of time for a single temperature step. The elongation is stable after about 20min for a temperature step of 4°C . This time span of 20min was thus taken as a minimum stabilization time for all experiments, since it suits the typically applied temperature increments. The resulting average heating rate was about $0.15^\circ/\text{min}$ ($\sim 10^\circ/\text{hour}$). Results were compared to values given in the literature and to those obtained on a Perkin-Elmer thermomechanical analyzer (TMA) with smaller samples and a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Data reduction from interferograms was carried out according to the following procedure. The phase images were filtered with a routine that takes into account a 5×5 pixel area around the pixel of concern and preserves the phase information. Images with high noise levels were filtered using a 6×6 filter. The deformation fields can be evaluated from the filtered phase images along a line or

Figure 4. Thermal expansion measurements: determining the required stabilization time

over an entire area. A tilt correction can be performed during the evaluation of the phase images, in order to remove displacements due to rigid body translations and rotations. Since the method gives a relative displacement field over a surface, average deformations were evaluated along evenly spaced tracks forming a grid over the sample area. The reported CTEs are the mean of five tracks. The thermal strains were obtained by dividing the relative displacement (peak/valley) of the ends of a track by the track length.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A first series of measurements was carried out on materials with documented CTEs: microscopy slide glass, stainless steel, copper, aluminum, and PC. The CTEs of these materials as measured by ESPI, over a range from 20 - 100°C and spanning values of 6.7-68.3x10⁻⁶/°C, correspond well with tabulated values, and were considered to validate the method. The CTEs were measured for both heating and cooling cycles. Although it was found that a better thermal homogeneity and stability were obtained for the cooling cycle, consistent values could be obtained during heating. These are given in Table 2. The values of the CTEs for the other materials for range between 20 and 110°C are summarized in Table 2 along with values obtained by TMA or from the literature.

Table 2. CTEs of homogeneous isotropic materials as measured by ESPI.

Material	Temp. range, °C	CTE (ESPI) x10 ⁻⁶ /°C	CTE (TMA) x10 ⁻⁶ /°C	CTE (tab.) x10 ⁻⁶ /°C
glass	20-80	6.7	--	5.5
stainless steel	20-80	15.6	--	16
copper	20-80	17.6	--	17.7
aluminum	20-80	24.2	--	24
polycarbonate, PC	20-100	68.3	69.0	68
polyetherimide, PEI	20-80	46.5	49.9	51.9
Dendrimer-modified epoxy, Tg=45°C	25-75	77.8 / 174*	62 / 168-193 ##*	--
PP/glass GMT, directions 1 / 2	20-100	13-16 / 19.5-26	26.6 / 27.5	--
ICI Plytron, ⊥ to fibers	25-57/57-101	103.1	98.4 / 121.9	92 / 100**
ø6mm CFRP wire, ⊥ to fibers	20-65	39.7-41.4	--	--
ø6mm AFRP wire, ⊥ to fibers	20-65	76.6-81.7	--	--
APC2, ⊥ to fibers	20-100	29.0 ±0.6	28.5	30.19
APC2, // to fibers	20-100	<1	-0	0.24
UD PEI/glass, ⊥ / // to fibers	20-100	23.5	29.4 ±1.0 / 7.4	--

* below / above Tg

** manuf. data sheet

APC2 data given in [3]

For most of the materials tested, the CTEs obtained by ESPI are very close to those measured by TMA or given in the literature or data sheets. The ESPI results tend to lie slightly lower than the others. This is because the present method gives the CTE as a function of temperature for small temperature steps. It is therefore an incremental value, referred to the length of the track at the beginning of each step, rather than the cumulative expansion over a large temperature interval referred to the temperature at the beginning of the test, as is for example the case with TMA. The scatter in the ESPI data typically lies around ±2-5% of the measured values.

Several difference exist between the present method and conventional methods such as TMA. First, no mechanical load besides the bearing stresses due to self-weight acts on the sample with the present ESPI method. This is quite advantageous in view of the errors due to probe contact pressure in TMA, as evidenced by the marks sometimes left on the surface even with minimal operating probe forces. Further, in TMA the CTE is obtained by a piecewise linear regression on

Figure 5. Thermal expansion of a dendrimer-modified epoxy: ESPI (left) vs TMA (right)

Figure 6. Length(Temp) curves for a dendrimer-modified epoxy as measured by ESPI and TMA

the $L(T)$ curve, where $L(T)$, the sample length as a function of temperature, is measured in very small increments of temperature. On the other hand, taking a point-by-point derivative of the curve gives a $CTE(T)$ plot with a high noise level. In the present ESPI method, the length increment of the sample is measured for temperature steps adapted to the material's expected thermal expansion to obtain a point-by-point plot of the CTE. The step size is chosen based for example on the previous measurement, or based on feedback, by observing the number of fringes obtained during a measurement step. The resulting curve can then be integrated to obtain the $L(T)$ curve. The scatter in the ESPI data is significantly smaller than in the TMA data. The dL/dT vs. temperature graphs obtained for a dendrimer-modified epoxy by the ESPI method are compared to the curves obtained by TMA in Fig.5. The resulting L vs. temperature plots, given in Fig.6, correspond very closely.

REQUIREMENTS FOR AN EFFECTIVE USE OF THE METHOD

An effective and reliable use of ESPI for the thermal expansion characterization of polymers and composites requires certain precautions. Given the high sensitivity of the ESPI measurements, the principal concerns are the stability of the experimental setup, the proper dimensioning of the samples, and an appropriate thermal loading program. Once the optical part of the system has been optimized, the positioning of the ESPI unit with respect to the sample must be rigid and free of vibrations. The sample size and the viewing field must be adapted to the expected deformations. The measurement procedure requires quasistatic conditions, i.e. load steps rather than a continuous ramp. The size of the temperature steps must be adjusted to provide an optimal number of interferences fringes in order to increase the signal-to-noise ratio and to avoid decorrelation of the speckle patterns. The noise level due to the speckle pattern makes measurement of high displacement gradients, i.e. with high fringe densities unreliable. This can be compensated by working with smaller loading steps and summing the contributions of the various steps by an image analysis routine that effectuates a phase addition of the successive interferograms.

A major difficulty encountered in the development of the present method was to ensure the stability and homogeneity of the temperature around the sample. Temperature gradients in the space between the sample and the camera result in thermal convection eddies that give rise to blurred images and transient, fictive fringes. These fringes are caused by bending of the light beams, and seriously distort the fringes carrying the information on the deformation of the sample. Great

improvements could be achieved in the present case through the oven design. The cylindrical geometry and lateral heating adopted here reduces air currents transverse to the viewing direction due to temperature gradients within the oven. The 75mm thickness of ceramic foam insulation has a thermal inertia giving a compromise between quick heat-up and stability of temperature in time. The weak point in the insulation of the test setup is the observation window. Despite multiple pane glass, the external surface of the window heated up slightly, causing some convection above the oven. This problem is reduced by placing a cylindrical sleeve around the opening (see Fig.3).

The CTE measurements could be improved by conducting the experiments under partial vacuum. This, however, involves a more complicated and costly setup, and problems in heating the samples homogeneously, e.g. by an infrared heat source. Placing the optics inside the oven could help in some instances, provided the warming of the mirror supports does not cause changes in their position and shape. A more appropriate solution would be to reduce the size of openings in the oven to a minimum, with separate windows for each imaging beam and for viewing. The temperature control would furthermore be improved by reducing the size of the test volume. These last two solutions were not adopted in the present case, since a greater flexibility in experimental geometries than they would allow was desired. From the data acquisition point of view, the noise due to turbulence could be reduced by taking a series of images over a larger span of time and obtaining the averaged phase image. Transient features due to the eddies would thus be reduced, and the signal due only to actual deformations would become clearer.

The range of CTEs that can be measured is determined by the sample size, the measuring sensitivity of the setup, and limits on the temperature step size. The main compromise in the sample size is between a large area for a higher number of fringes and less noise, and smaller samples to obtain a more local measurement and thus reduce the extent of turbulence over the considered area. For lower CTEs, larger samples and/or temperature steps are needed in order to obtain clear interferograms. In the case of the 15x15mm² glass samples, for example, steps of 20°C were applied. For small temperature steps, the precision of the temperature achieved is the principal source of error. In the present case, a temperature control with $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ means that an error up to $\pm 5\%$ is possible for a step of 2°C, in particular when the temperature cycle is not monotonic. For materials with higher CTEs, it is therefore advantageous to conduct measurements on a smaller sample area and with a lower sensitivity, in order to keep the temperature step size larger.

The precision of the measurements depends strongly on the heating program. It was found that an optimized heating cycle, in temperature steps adapted to the expected CTE, followed by a sufficient stabilization time, was extremely important for reliable measurements, especially at higher temperatures. Since the deformations are obtained by correlation of two successive interference patterns, any change in the surface micro-topography results in a loss of information. When conducting tests at higher temperatures, it is therefore important to ensure that the sample and the surface coating are dry, in order to avoid changes in the surface due to evaporation of water.

Speckle pattern interferometry is subject to certain inherent limitations to its resolution and precision. The sensitivity, which is given by the wavelength of the laser used for the measurements and the setup geometry, can be improved only to a limited extent for a given installation. Since the luminosity of each speckle consists of a contribution from every point on the surface, even slight, local disturbances cause variations in the speckle intensity, which in turn increase the noise which is already inherent to the speckle pattern. Further, as was already addressed above, the correlation limit for the speckle pattern means that any rigid body motion of the sample superimposed on the deformation must remain very small. Finally, the spatial resolution, defined by the optics and in particular the pitch of the video camera, limits the size of the smallest features which can be imaged. The smallest sample size on which the CTE was measured here was $\phi 6\text{mm}$.

CONCLUSIONS

Electronic speckle pattern interferometry (ESPI) has been applied successfully to the measurement of the thermal expansion coefficients of composite materials. The CTE of a wide range of metals, polymers, and composites was obtained as a function of temperature over the range 20-110°C, for both heating and cooling. The results compare very favorably with conventional dilatometer (TMA) results. The method however allows a wider range of possibilities, among which larger sample sizes and aspect ratios. The full field capability of the method makes even the thermal

expansion of entire parts with complex shapes possible [11]. Finally, as it is contactless, it is ideally suited for the measurement of the CTE through the glass transition of polymers, as was shown here with the modified epoxy.

The method has several notable advantages. Sample preparation is simple and quick. Very small deformations can be measured without contact to the sample. The method is applicable to a large range of sample sizes and shapes. Finally, ESPI allows a rapid measurement of the CTE along several axes. The disadvantages are that the method is sensitive to disturbances such as vibrations and strong thermal gradients and turbulences. The latter limits the temperature range over which measurements can be made up to date. A vibration damping installation and careful control of the thermal environment are therefore essential to obtain high quality results. The results support the applicability of this method to a broad range of tests in which surface deformations resulting from thermal as well as mechanical loading are of interest.

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